

MACHINED SURFACE TOPOGRAPHY ANALYSIS IN ULTRASONIC VIBRATION ASSISTED END GRINDING OF SiCp/Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The surface quality in ultrasonic vibration assisted end grinding of SiCp/Al composites is important as it influences the performance of the finished surface to a great extent. This paper presents a comprehensive analysis to characterize the machined surface topography with 3D surface roughness (S_q , S_{sk} and S_{tr}) and 3D surface dimension D_s . The results show that the main factors influencing surface roughness S_q is the spindle speed and followed by vibration amplitude, cutting depth and feedrate. Surface fractal dimension D_s represents the ability of space filling of the machined surface and shows a weak-negative correlation with surface roughness S_q . Compared with S_q , D_s is more sensitive to the pit which is the main defect of machined surface. A large value of surface fractal dimension D_s corresponds to a better and exquisite surface finish. The main factors effecting the surface fractal dimension D_s are spindle speed and feedrate, and influencing degree of these two factors is similar. The influence order of process parameters on D_s is: feedrate > spindle speed > vibration amplitude > cutting depth.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, SiCp/Al composites have been widely used in aerospace, automotive industries and electronics industries due to their good material properties, such as light weight, high specific strength and elastic modulus, excellent wear resistance, and low thermal expansion coefficient. However, this kind of composites is well known as poor machinability and high machining costs, since the reinforcement particles are significantly harder than the commonly used tools. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a non-traditional machining process to meet the demand of SiCp/Al composites machining. Ultrasonic vibration assisted end grinding, as shown in Fig. 1, has excellent characteristics in grinding difficult-to-process materials for the vibrational cutting is a discontinuous process which can significantly reduce the grinding force and heat [1]. The motion trajectories of grains on end surface of the grinding tool are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of ultrasonic vibration assisted end grinding

Figure 2: The motion trajectories of grains on end surface of the grinding tool

Surface topography is one of the foremost characteristics of the surface integrity and has been extensively studied in the last decade [2-17]. In the studies on surface topography of milling or

grinding of SiCp/Al composites, in most cases, only 2D surface roughness parameter Ra is widely used. Reddy et al. [8] presented an experimental research on end milling of Al alloy reinforced with SiC using TiAlN coated carbide end mill cutters. The results showed that the surface roughness increased with an increase in feed and decreased with the increase in cutting speed rate.

Zhou et al. [12] investigated the effects of grinding depth and speed on surface roughness in grinding of SiCp/Al composites applied liquid nitrogen. The results showed that the variations of grinding depth and speed of worktable did not affect the average surface roughness significantly. And the average surface roughness obtained under the wet grinding condition was much higher than that under the cryogenic condition.

Li et al. [13] made an attempt to investigate the effects of cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut, with the same change of material removal rate (MRR) on the mill-grinding force and surface roughness of SiCp/Al composites based on the experimental study using mill-grinding processing method. It could also be concluded that surface roughness value in mill-grinding of SiCp/Al composites increased by increasing the depth of cut and feed rate, respectively. The significant increase of surface roughness might be due to the combination effect of increasing the feed rate and depth of cut simultaneously.

Bian et al. [14] presented a study on the surface quality including surface roughness and surface topography in precision milling of SiCp/Al composites with a single flute monocrystalline diamond end mill. It was found that surface roughness showed an increasing trend with the increase of feed per tooth. And the same conclusion was also obtained by Yang et al. [15], who investigated the machined surface quality of SiCp/Al composites in milling grooves with PCD tools of different grain sizes.

Wang et al. [16] studied the surface roughness in rotary ultrasonic face grinding of SiCp/Al composites. The same as conventional grinding progress, surface roughness increased with feedrate increasing. But he found that Ra fluctuated in a range with cutting speed and cutting depth increasing. It was unlike the conventional grinding of ductile metal material, in which surface roughness decreased with cutting speed increasing and cutting depth decreasing.

However, first of all, 2D surface roughness is only statistic value of surface profile traces and could not depict a three dimensional surface essentially. For instance, the opposite conclusion of the influence of cutting depth on surface roughness were obtained in Ref. [14] and Ref. [15]. In Ref. [14], surface roughness increased with cutting depth increasing, while in Ref. [15], surface roughness decreased. Secondly, the values of 2D surface roughness of different surface areas on the same machined surface are often different [18]. This is due to that the surface generation is a random progress, and the defects such as pits, cracks are often randomly distributed on the machined surface. So different measured areas will yield different values of 2D surface roughness Ra, i.e., the measurement values of Ra have a great deal of randomness. For this reason, in Ref. [16], surface roughness Ra measured with cutting speed and cutting depth increasing fluctuates in a certain range. In conclusion, 3D surface roughness parameters, which have the same dimension with machined surface, are suitable for evaluation of topography characteristics of SiCp/Al composites surface.

Meanwhile, surface topography is a non-stationary random process for which the variance of the height distribution of roughness features is related to the length of the sample. Unfortunately, as statistical parameters, both 2D surface roughness parameters and 3D surface roughness parameters all depend on sampling lengths and the instrumental resolution, and could not exactly depict the characteristics of SiCp/Al machined surface which including grooves, cracks, pits and so on. So another evaluation parameter must be introduced to solve this problem.

Fractals retain all the structural information. Thus as a scale-invariant parameter, fractal dimension can be a good choice to evaluate the intrinsic characteristic of nonlinear phenomena. Fractal geometry is characterized by single descriptor, the fractal dimension, which consists of surface fractal dimension D_s and profile fractal dimension D_f . Different from the topological dimension of conventional geometry, surface fractal dimension D_s is the non-integer within the range $2 < D_s < 3$, while profile fractal dimension D_f is within the range from 1 up to 2.

Based on available references, very few studies focused on 3D surface roughness or surface fractal evaluation of surface topography of SiCp/Al composites. Wang et al. [19] selected typical 2D (R_a and R_z) and 3D (S_a and S_q) surface roughness parameters to evaluate the influence of the milling parameters on the surface quality. The results indicated that 3D parameters (S_a and S_q) were more

capable to describe the influence of the milling parameters, and among them S_q was preferable due to its good sensitivity. S_q decreased with milling speed and increased with feed rate.

Muguthu et al.[20] investigated the effect of process parameters on profile fractal dimension in precision turning of SiCp/Al composites with three triangular-shaped cutting tools such as coated CBN, uncoated CBN and PCD. The results showed that profile fractal dimension decreased with increase in cutting speed for uncoated CBN and coated CBN tools. For PCD tool, profile fractal dimension increased with increase in cutting speed. For all the tools, an increase in depth of cut had a corresponding decrease in profile fractal dimension. On fractal characterization of surface in machining MMCs, PCD tools gave better results compared with CBN tools. But in this study, only profile fractal dimension was used, which was not enough to evaluate the surface fractal characteristics.

Now it is clear that further research is needed to evaluate the characteristics of surface topography in machining of SiCp/Al composites. This paper presents $L_{25}(5^4)$ orthogonal experiments to investigate the influence of the process parameters, including spindle speed, feedrate, cutting depth and vibration amplitude, on the machined surface in ultrasonic vibration assisted end grinding of SiCp/Al composites by the use of 3D surface roughness and surface fractal dimension, and discusses the relationship between 3D surface roughness and surface fractal dimension. At last, the optimum conditions are obtained based on range analysis of the results of the $L_{25}(5^4)$ orthogonal experiments. Selection and calculation of 3D surface roughness and fractal dimension will be introduced in the following section.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND PROCEDURE

2.1 Experimental equipment

Fig. 3 presents the experimental setup used in this work. Ultrasonic vibration assisted end grinding experiments were conducted on an ultrasonic vibration machine center (DMG Ultrasonic 70-5 linear), which consisted a numerical control system, an ultrasonic spindle system, a data acquisition system and a coolant system. The maximum spindle speed was 18000rev/min. The frequency and amplitude supplied to the tool in the z direction were about 30 kHz and $5\mu\text{m}$ respectively. The grinding tool with metal-bonded diamond abrasives was provided by SCHOTT Company, and its properties were listed in Table 1.

2.2 Workpiece material

The workpiece material was 45% SiCp/Al2024 composites. The average diameter of SiC particles was $5\mu\text{m}$. Fig. 4 showed the microstructure of SiCp/Al composites.

Figure 3: Experimental setup

Figure 4: The microstructure of SiCp/Al composites

Abrasive size s (μm)	Abrasive concentration Ca	Outer radius R_o (mm)	Inner radius R_i (mm)
75	100	3	2

Table 1: Process variables of the $L_{25}(5^4)$ orthogonal experiments

2.3 Experiment

$L_{25}(5^4)$ orthogonal experiments based on these four factors with five levels were conducted, as listed in Table 2. The machined surface of SiCp/Al composites was measured by LSCM (laser scanning confocal microscope) type OLS3000 with scanning square areas of $128\mu\text{m} \times 128\mu\text{m}$. According to 3D variational method, surface fractal dimension D_s was calculated with MATLAB software based on surface data.

Process variables		Levels
Spindle speed n (rev/min)	A	3000, 6000, 9000, 12000, 15000
Feed rate v_f (mm/min)	B	5, 10, 15, 20, 25
Cutting depth a_p (μm)	C	5, 10, 15, 20, 25
Vibration amplitude A (μm)	D	0, 1.25, 2.5, 3.75, 5
Cutting width b (mm)		6

Table 2: Process variables of the $L_{25}(5^4)$ orthogonal experiments

No.	A	B	C	D	D_s	S_q	S_{sk}	S_{tr}
1	3000	5	5	0	2.651723	0.275272	-0.662150	0.708030
2	3000	10	10	1.25	2.623557	0.299451	-0.903220	0.383200
3	3000	15	15	2.5	2.577243	0.331216	-0.562780	0.747110
4	3000	20	20	3.75	2.776217	0.345040	-1.507710	0.307190
5	3000	25	25	5	2.690275	0.311749	-3.314400	0.161720
6	6000	5	5	2.5	2.702005	0.222427	-1.053530	0.880620
7	6000	10	10	3.75	2.648257	0.250343	-1.936650	0.747920
8	6000	15	15	5	2.625588	0.279708	-1.857110	0.806740
9	6000	20	20	0	2.594615	0.387664	-0.808850	0.599360
10	6000	25	25	1.25	2.604805	0.322034	-1.837750	0.629800
11	9000	5	5	5	2.655425	0.217733	-1.897970	0.469060
12	9000	10	10	0	2.666889	0.270950	-0.015140	0.612520
13	9000	15	15	1.25	2.636704	0.295674	-0.711230	0.573350
14	9000	20	20	2.5	2.802874	0.375353	-0.290280	0.323700
15	9000	25	25	3.75	2.825909	0.327895	-0.730970	0.083230
16	12000	5	5	1.25	2.570126	0.361990	-0.657100	0.750620
17	12000	10	10	2.5	2.601270	0.390043	-1.538960	0.791670
18	12000	15	15	3.75	2.654570	0.249664	-1.986390	0.744740
19	12000	20	20	5	2.726022	0.175428	-1.324670	0.491170
20	12000	25	25	0	2.668559	0.338245	-3.495250	0.777580
21	15000	5	5	3.75	2.662390	0.226654	-0.135460	0.557930
22	15000	10	10	5	2.701755	0.272480	-0.731660	0.131770
23	15000	15	15	0	2.666370	0.310830	-0.568390	0.348620
24	15000	20	20	1.25	2.728900	0.178582	-0.422340	0.186140
25	15000	25	25	2.5	2.738540	0.167860	-0.369510	0.390990

Table 3: The results of the $L_{25}(5^4)$ orthogonal experiments

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Influence of process parameters on 3D surface roughness

3.1.1 Influence of process parameters on S_q

The results of the $L_{25}(5^4)$ orthogonal experiments were shown in Table 3. Fig. 5 presents the influences of process parameters including cutting depth, feedrate, spindle speed and vibration amplitude on 3D surface roughness S_q .

Fig. 5 (a) shows the influence of spindle speed on S_q . It is clear that S_q decreases with spindle speed in the range of 3000-6000rev/min, and then approximately linearly and slowly increases with an

increase of spindle speed until the spindle speed reaches a value of 12000rev/min, at last it rapidly declines when the spindle speed exceeds 12000rev/min. This is because with the increase of spindle speed, the effective cutting time of a single grain on the grinding tool is shortened, machining becomes more adiabatic and the heat generated in the shear zone cannot be conducted away. A high value of temperature will soften the Aluminum alloy matrix and thus promotes the grain boundary dislocation, which contributes to easier chip formation of Aluminum alloy matrix. Hence, the grinding force is reduced and a lower value of surface roughness is obtained. Fig. 6 presents the 3D surface topographies of SiCp/Al composites in different spindle speed conditions. The other three parameters are: $v_f=15\text{mm/min}$, $a_p=10\mu\text{m}$ and $A=5\mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 5 (b) shows the influence of feedrate on S_q . It is clear that S_q increases with cutting depth increasing from 5mm/min to 15mm/min, and then keeps stable until feedrate reaches a value of 25mm/min. On the one hand, this is attributed to the fact that a large feedrate value results in a high residual stress and this cause to decrease bonding effect between SiC particles and Al alloy matrix, which makes SiC particles tend to be broken down or be pulled out, hence the surface roughness increases. On the other hand, with the feedrate increasing, the undeformed chip thickness increases, which results in an increase in grinding force and surface roughness. When the feedrate exceeds 15mm/min, it has no significantly influence on S_q . Fig. 7 presents the 3D surface topographies of SiCp/Al composites in different feedrate conditions. The other three parameters are: $n=12000\text{rev/min}$, $a_p=10\mu\text{m}$ and $A=5\mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 5 (c) shows the influence of cutting depth on S_q . It is clear that S_q decreases with an increase of cutting depth in the range of 5-15 μm . The possible reason is that the phenomena of rubbing and plowing gradually decline when cutting depth increases [16]. And then S_q increases until cutting depth reaches a value of 25 μm . This is due to that with the increase of cutting depth, the removal material volume per unit time increases which causes the rise of grinding force and temperature in the cutting zone significantly, and results in an increase in surface roughness. Fig. 8 presents the 3D surface topographies of SiCp/Al composites in different cutting depth conditions. The other three parameters are: $n=12000\text{rev/min}$, $v_f=15\text{mm/min}$ and $A=5\mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 5 (d) shows the influence of vibration amplitude on S_q . It is clear that in general S_q rapidly decreases with an increase of vibration amplitude. This is because in end grinding process, the grinding tool is not in continuous contact with the workpiece due to ultrasonic vibration. So there are composed of two different material removal modes between the abrasive grains and SiCp/Al composites: impact and erosion, as shown in Fig. 9. On the one hand, under the influence of high frequency ultrasonic vibration, the impacts of the grinding tool on the workpiece yielded a large number of microcracks, which facilitate material removal and the expansion of cracks, and large SiC particles are broken down into small chips. On the other hand, with the increase of the vibration amplitude, the effect of planishing plays a predominant role in the machining process which makes Al alloy matrix soften and the surface roughness reduced. Fig. 10 presents the 3D surface topographies of SiCp/Al composites in different vibration amplitude conditions. The other three parameters are: $n=12000\text{rev/min}$, $v_f=15\text{mm/min}$ and $a_p=10\mu\text{m}$.

a

b

c

d

Figure 5: Influences of process parameters on S_q

a

b

Figure 6: 3D surface topographies of SiCp/Al composites in different spindle speed conditions: $n=3000\text{rev/min}$ (a) and $n=15000\text{rev/min}$ (b)

a

b

Figure 7: 3D surface topographies of SiCp/Al composites in different feedrate conditions: $v_f=5\text{mm/min}$ (a) and $v_f=25\text{mm/min}$ (b)

Figure 8: 3D surface topographies of SiCp/Al composites in different cutting depth conditions: $a_p=5\mu\text{m}$ (a) and $a_p=25\mu\text{m}$ (b)

Figure 9: Material removal mode: the interaction of impact and erosion

Figure 10: 3D surface topographies of SiCp/Al composites in different vibration amplitudes conditions: $A=0$ (a) and $A=5\mu\text{m}$ (b)

3.1.2 Influence of process parameters on S_{sk}

S_{sk} is used to describe amplitude characteristic in statistics. If $S_{sk} > 0$, it indicates that the topography has more crests or crests are sharpness meanwhile troughs are flat. In contrast, if $S_{sk} < 0$, topography has more troughs or troughs are sharpness meanwhile crests are flat.

Fig. 11 shows the influence of process parameters on S_{sk} . It can be seen from Fig. 11 that the values of S_{sk} in all process conditions are negative, it indicates that the pit generated due to pulled-out, rotated or crushed SiC particles is the main defect on the machined surface of SiCp/Al composites, as shown in Fig. 12.

Figure 11: Influence of process parameters on S_{sk}

Figure 12: The pits on the machined surface of SiCp/Al composites

3.1.2 Influence of process parameters on S_{tr}

S_{tr} is used to describe the texture characteristic of the machined surface. If $S_{tr} > 0.5$, it indicates that the machined surface is isotropic. In contrast, if $S_{tr} < 0.3$, the machined surface is nonisotropic.

Fig. 13 shows the influence of process parameters on S_{tr} . It can be seen from Fig. 13 that in most cases, the values of S_{tr} are larger than 0.5, and at the same time there are eleven points below the Dash Dot line ($S_{tr}=0.5$). Among them, the values of seven points are in the range of 0.3 up to 0.5 which indicate that the seven machined surfaces are weak-nonisotropic. While the other four points are below the Short Dash line ($S_{tr}=0.3$) which indicate that the four machined surfaces are nonisotropic. It is noted that, surface fractal dimension D_s is often simply calculated by one plus the profile fractal dimension D_f in the available publications, this can bring considerable errors for this calculation method is only suitable for isotropic surface. So development of the 3D method to calculate surface fractal dimension D_s for both isotropic and nonisotropic surfaces is necessary and correct.

Figure 13: Influences of process parameters on S_{tr}

Figure 14: Relationship between 3D surface roughness S_q and surface fractal dimension D_s

3.2 Relationship between surface roughness S_q and surface fractal dimension D_s

Relationship between surface roughness S_q and surface fractal dimension D_s is presented in Fig. 14. It can be observed that in most cases surface fractal dimension D_s shows a weak-negative correlation with surface roughness S_q . But the relationship was not strictly consistent, that is to say, there is no one to one correspondence between the two parameters. The existing of points P_1 (No.15), P_2 (No.14) and P_3 (No.4) which are far away from the fitting curve indicates that surface roughness and fractal dimension are different kind of evaluation parameters. It can be seen that there exists two points P_4 (No.5) and surface P_5 (No.23) which have similar values of S_q . Surface P_4 is with a large value of D_s , and surface P_5 has a small value of D_s . 3D surface topographies of surface P_4 and surface P_5 are shown in Fig. 15. It can be seen that a large number of obvious pits are found in surface P_5 , while surface P_4 shows a relative smooth surface. That is to say, surface dimension D_s , compared with statistical parameter surface roughness S_q , is more sensitive to the change of microstructure of machined surface, such as defects, and a large value of surface fractal dimension D_s corresponds to a better and exquisite surface finish. The relationship between defects and surface fractal dimension D_s is discussed in the following section.

Figure 15: 3D surface topographies of surface P₄ (a) and P₅ (b)

3.3 Relationship between defects and surface fractal dimension D_s

Surface fractal dimension D_s represents the ability of space filling of the machined surface and shows a positive correlation with the space expansion of microstructure. Metal-bonded diamond abrasives are randomly distributed on the grinding tool and the shape of every abrasive is complicated and different from each other. The combined action of repeatedly micro scratching of diamond abrasives and tool-workpiece interactions results in the formation of the complicated micro topography and fractal characteristics of machined surface. Surface fractal dimension will finally achieve a stable value in a certain grinding process condition, that is to say, one kind of process condition will be correspondence to one kind of fractal characteristic.

As the grinding process continues in a good condition, the microstructures fill the machined surface, the fractal characteristics become more obvious. Many new exquisitely smooth microstructures with less defects are formed on the top surface and induces the large surface fractal dimension. However, the worsening process conditions will result in many defects, such as pits, cracks and grooves on the machined surface of SiCp/Al composites. Among them, pits generated due to pulled-out, rotated or crushed SiC particles is the main defect on the machined surface of SiCp/Al composites, as mentioned in Section 4.1.2. Thus the break of original microstructures forms the roughness microstructures with defects, and marked differences in topographies among these two microstructures are generated. The pits induce an obvious decrease in the space filling of machined surface, thus surface fractal dimension D_s gives fast response and decreases significantly. These can explain why surface fractal dimension D_s is more sensitive to the defect of machined surface of SiCp/Al composites.

Figs. 16 and 17 present the relationship between pits and surface fractal dimension D_s . It can be seen that surface fractal dimension D_s decreases with an increase in the number and size of pits, this conclusion agrees well with the above analysis.

Figure 16: Relationship between pits number and surface fractal dimension D_s : N=1 (a), N=2 (b) and N=3 (c)

Figure 17: Relationship between pits size and surface fractal dimension D_s : small (a), medium (b) and big (c)

3.4 Range analysis of surface roughness S_q and surface fractal dimension D_s

Table 4 shows the range analysis results of $L_{25}(5^4)$ orthogonal experiments. The larger the R_j , the greater the influence of the factor on surface roughness S_q and surface fractal dimension D_s . The results of Table 4 show that the main factors influencing S_q is spindle speed, followed by vibration amplitude, cutting depth and feedrate. Then the optimum conditions for obtaining a minimum value of S_q can be obtained: spindle speed $n = 15000\text{rev}/\text{min}$, vibration amplitude $A = 5\mu\text{m}$, cutting depth $a_p = 15\mu\text{m}$ and feedrate $f = 5\text{mm}/\text{min}$. For D_s , the main factors are spindle speed and feedrate, and the two factors have similar influence. The influence order of process parameters on D_s is: feedrate > spindle speed > vibration amplitude > cutting depth. Then the optimum conditions for obtaining a maximum

valve of D_s can be obtained: feedrate $f = 20\text{mm/min}$, spindle speed $n = 9000\text{rev/min}$, vibration amplitude $A = 3.75\mu\text{m}$ and cutting depth $a_p = 10\mu\text{m}$.

	A	B	C	D
S_q				
k_1	0.312546	0.260815	0.298961	0.316592
k_2	0.292435	0.296653	0.267206	0.291546
k_3	0.297521	0.293418	0.263224	0.297380
k_4	0.303074	0.292413	0.285110	0.279919
k_5	0.231281	0.293557	0.322357	0.251420
R_j	0.081264	0.035838	0.059133	0.065173
D_s				
k_1	2.663803	2.648334	2.683145	2.649631
k_2	2.635054	2.648346	2.708773	2.632818
k_3	2.717560	2.632095	2.655677	2.684386
k_4	2.644109	2.725726	2.675472	2.713469
k_5	2.699591	2.705618	2.637051	2.679813
R_j	0.073451	0.073523	0.046095	0.063837

Table 4: Range analysis of the $L_{25}(5^4)$ orthogonal experiments

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, $L_{25}(5^4)$ orthogonal experiments based on four factors with five levels were conducted to study the surface topography of machined surface in ultrasonic vibration assisted end grinding of SiCp/Al composites by using 3D surface roughness parameters (S_q , S_{sk} and S_{tr}) and surface fractal dimension D_s . The following conclusions are obtained:

1. The main factors influencing surface roughness S_q is spindle speed and followed by vibration amplitude, cutting depth and feedrate. S_q is found to decrease with an increase in spindle speed and vibration amplitude. S_q increases with the feedrate in the range of 5mm/min to 15mm/min, and then keeps stable until feedrate reaches a value of 25mm/min. S_q decreases with an increase in cutting depth in the range of 5-15 μm and increases until cutting depth reaches a value of 25 μm . The optimum conditions for obtaining a minimum valve of S_q are: spindle speed $n = 15000\text{rev/min}$, vibration amplitude $A = 5\mu\text{m}$, cutting depth $a_p = 15\mu\text{m}$ and feedrate $f = 5\text{mm/min}$.

2. Surface fractal dimension D_s represents the ability of space filling of the machined surface and shows a weak-negative correlation with surface roughness S_q . Compared with S_q , D_s is more sensitive to the defect of the machined surface of SiCp/Al composites. A large value of D_s corresponds to a better and exquisite surface finish.

3. The main factors influencing surface fractal dimension D_s are spindle speed and feedrate, and influencing degree of these two factors is similar. The influencing order of process parameters on D_s is: feedrate > spindle speed > vibration amplitude > cutting depth. The optimum conditions for obtaining a maximum valve of D_s are: feedrate $f = 20\text{mm/min}$, spindle speed $n = 9000\text{rev/min}$, vibration amplitude $A = 3.75\mu\text{m}$ and cutting depth $a_p = 10\mu\text{m}$.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Zhou M, Zheng W. A model for grinding forces prediction in ultrasonic vibration assisted grinding of SiCp/Al composites. *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, **87(9)**, 2016, pp. 3211-3224 (doi:10.1007/s00170-016-8726-x).
- [2] Kannan S, Kishawy HA. Surface characteristics of machined aluminium metal matrix composites. *Int J Mach Tool Manu*, **46(15)**, 2006, pp. 2017-2025 (doi:10.1016/j.ijmachtools.2006.01.003).

- [3] Dabade UA, Joshi SS, Balasubramaniam R, Bhanuprasad VV. Surface finish and integrity of machined surfaces on Al/SiCp composites. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. **192**, 2007, pp. 166-174 ().
- [4] Palanikumar K, Karthikeyan R. Assessment of factors influencing surface roughness on the machining of Al/SiC particulate composites. *Mater Design*, **28(5)**, 2007, pp. 1584-1591 (doi:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2007.04.044).
- [5] Ge YF, Xu JH, Yang H, Luo SB, Fu Y. Workpiece surface quality when ultra-precision turning of SiCp/Al composites. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, **203(1-3)**, 2008, pp. 166-175 (doi:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2007.09.070).
- [6] Ozben T, Kilickap E, Cakir O. Investigation of mechanical and machinability properties of SiC particle reinforced Al-MMC. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, **198(1-3)**, 2008, pp. 220-225 (doi:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2007.06.082).
- [7] Pramanik A, Zhang LC, Arsecularatne JA. Machining of metal matrix composites: Effect of ceramic particles on residual stress, surface roughness and chip formation. *Int J Mach Tool Manu*, **48(15)**, 2008, pp. 1613-1625 (doi:10.1016/j.ijmachtools.2008.07.008).
- [8] Reddy NSK, Kwang-Sup S, Yang MY. Experimental study of surface integrity during end milling of Al/SiC particulate metal-matrix composites. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, **201(1-3)**, 2008, pp. 574-579 (doi:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2007.11.280).
- [9] Kannan S, Kishawy HA, Deiab I. Cutting forces and TEM analysis of the generated surface during machining metal matrix composites. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, **209(5)**, 2009, pp. 2260-2269 (doi:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2008.05.025).
- [10] Bhushan RK, Kumar S, Das S. Effect of machining parameters on surface roughness and tool wear for 7075 Al alloy SiC composite. *Int J Adv Manuf Tech*, **50(5-8)**, 2010, pp. 459-469 (doi:10.1007/s00170-010-2529-2).
- [11] Dong GJ, Zhang HJ, Zhou M, Zhang YJ. Experimental investigation on ultrasonic vibration-assisted turning of SiCp/Al composites. *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, **28(9)**, 2013, pp. 999-1002 (doi:10.1080/10426914.2012.709338).
- [12] Zhou L, Huang ST, Yu XL. Machining characteristics in cryogenic grinding of SiCp/Al composites. *Acta Metall Sin-Engl*, **27(5)**, 2014, pp. 869-874 (doi:10.1007/s40195-014-0126-3).
- [13] Li JG, Du JG, Yao YX, Hao ZP, Liu X. Experimental study of machinability in mill-grinding of SiCp/Al composites. *J Wuhan Univ Technol*, **29(6)**, 2014, pp. 1104-1110 (doi:10.1007/s11595-014-1050-0).
- [14] Bian R, He N, Li L, Zhan ZB, Wu Q, Shi ZY. Precision milling of high volume fraction SiCp/Al composites with monocrystalline diamond end mill. *Int J Adv Manuf Tech*, **71(1-4)**, 2014, pp. 411-419 (doi:10.1007/s00170-013-5494-8).
- [15] Yang YF, Wu Q, Zhan ZB, Li L, He N, Shrestha R. An experimental study on milling of high-volume fraction SiCP/Al composites with PCD tools of different grain size. *Int J Adv Manuf Tech*, **79(9-12)**, 2015, pp. 1699-1705 (doi:10.1007/s00170-015-6901-0).
- [16] Zhou M, Wang M, Dong GJ. Experimental investigation on rotary ultrasonic face grinding of SiCp/Al composites. *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, **31(5)**, 2015, pp. 673-678 (doi:10.1080/10426914.2015.1025962).
- [17] Yu XL, Huang ST, Xu LF. ELID grinding characteristics of SiCp/Al composites. *Int J Adv Manuf Tech*, **86(5-8)**, 2016, pp. 1165-1171 (doi:10.1007/s00170-015-8235-3).
- [18] Wang YJ, Huang HB, Chen LG, Sun LN. Choice of reference surfaces for machined surface roughness in milling of SiCp/Al composites. *J Cent South Univ*, **21(11)**, 2014, pp. 4150-4156 (doi:10.1007/s11771-014-2410-9).
- [19] Wang T, Xie LJ, Wang XB, Shang TY. 2D and 3D milled surface roughness of high volume fraction SiCp/Al composites. *Def Technol*, **11(2)**, 2015, pp. 104-109 (doi:10.1016/j.dt.2015.01.001).
- [20] Muguthu JN, Gao D. Profile fractal dimension and dimensional accuracy analysis in machining metal matrix composites (MMCs). *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, **28(10)**, 2013, pp. 1102-1109 (doi:10.1080/10426914.2013.823501).